

قرآن کریم میں کلمہ فساد اور اسکی عصری معنویت

**THE WORD FASAAD IN HOLY QUR'AN AND IT'S
CONTEMPORARY MEANING****Ayesha Zainab (ORCID ID: 0009-0001-3148-7697)**

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ABSTRACT

Islam provides a comprehensive system for life and undoubtedly is a religion of love and peace. In fact, in this world, fasaad (Riot) finds its root in human desires, wealth, and land. Fasaad is a term encompassing various forms of degradation, misguidance, murder, polytheism, disbelief and all sorts of turmoil, as mentioned throughout the Quran in various instances where activities leading to corruption and destruction of justice in society are criticized.

Allah Ta'ala has placed the difference between good and bad, good and evil in human nature, as even before the creation of Adam, Allah instructed the angels that He would appoint a vicegerent on Earth. The angels questioned, "Will You place upon it one who causes corruption therein and sheds blood, while we declare your praise and sanctify you?" Allah responded, "Indeed, I know that which you do not know." Anyway in this context, we will discuss the concept of "fasaad" and its contemporary spiritual significance as portrayed in the Quran. The aim is to prevent fasaad and establish a society based on principles of justice.

Keywords: Corruption, Crime, Terrorism, Murder, Fitna, Fasad, Mischief, Riot.

کلیدی الفاظ: رشوت، فتنہ و فساد، جرم، دہشت گردی، قتل، فساد فی الارض، شرارت۔

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